

Total Capacity Annual Base Model

Transport Demand Base Model

Problems found

- DEMCARGSL and DEMCARELC capital cost has a peak between 2049 and 2050.
- DEMCARGSL capital cost increases from 0.001 to 975.04 (that is why in the graph the demand drastically falls)
- DEMCARELC capital cost decreases from 5581.63 to 0.001 (that is why in the graph the demand drastically increases).

Something interesting

- When the geothermal capacity was changed from 1.7 to 0.9, the distribution of energy generation completely changed.

